

Glossing the Margins: How Annotation Shaped Dictionaries, Encyclopedias, and Architectural Knowledge

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Abstract

There is a similarity between modes of knowledge production in medieval scripture, which fostered early encyclopedic compilations, and Renaissance architectural treatises. Both sought to describe and systematize knowledge while leaving space for personal annotations, enabling dialogue and critical interaction between the material and the reader's voice. Renaissance scholars applied a similar method to systematize architectural knowledge through annotated editions of Vitruvius, such as Da Sangallo's *Incunabulum* and Inigo Jones's *Quattro Libri*. This text traces how medieval glossing practices gradually produced structured dictionaries, and how architectural knowledge in the humanist tradition similarly emerged from acts of recording, comparing, and commenting, which aimed to create comprehensive bodies of knowledge and organized canons.

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Glossing the Dictionary in History, but what about Architectural Marginalia

The development of knowledge moves from irregular and often subjective - even fabulous descriptions - towards a sense of objectivity. Aided by speculation, experiment and logic. But it is also a process of collecting, comparing, commenting and especially annotating. This process becomes especially visible in historical examples of dictionaries, encyclopedias, and architectural treatises.

Both encyclopedists and architects helped move their fields from fragmentary, subjective accumulations toward structured knowledge systems. One important component to this development was the practice of annotation and glossing in the margins of books. The scribbles which were added on the pages periphery reveal not only personal thought processes but also something about the broader historical work of clarification, commentary, critique, and, above all, the re-ordering of knowledge. The history of marginalia shows how small accumulative acts of description, clarification, and definition gradually transformed scattered interests and observations into institutionalized disciplines with professional authority.

One of the earliest and best-known examples, of an encyclopedia, which lives between the phantasy and objectivity is the *Naturalis historia*, compiled by the Roman author, natural historian, philosopher, and military commander; Pliny the Elder. In the first century AD, he produced an encyclopedic accumulation of knowledge, collected from other authors, with articles on astronomy, geography, botany, and medicine. Everything was included in the compilation - large or small, fact or fiction, reality or myth - enriched with personal observations, experiences and opinions.² The book is structured along analogies, similarities and contrasts, which feel peculiar compared to modern taxonomies. For example Fish are ordered according to those “that have a pebble in their heads; Fish that hide in winter; Fish that feel the influence of the stars; Extraordinary prices paid for certain fish.”³

Practical advice is enriched with morality following patterns of thought rather than a logic inherent to the discussed topic. The *Naturalis Historia* would become somewhat of a prototype for encyclopedias

During the Middle Ages, it became common to annotate important, historical, philosophical, but especially religious and legal texts with comments and clarifications on difficult expressions or elaborations on complex themes. These annotations were called *glóssae*, which means “tongue” or “language” in Greek. And the glosses allowed a multitude of voices to be heard.

² Collison, Robert. *Encyclopaedias: Their History*, 21.

³ Murphy, *Pliny the Elder's Natural History*,

In the medieval imagination, the margins were wild and liminal zones where everything could flip upside down, and „paradox, pun and perversity, areas in which social and psychological conflicts could be played out“⁴ Glossing was also a method to engage with thoughts and ideas without being bound to time or geography.⁵ Scholars gathered the singular *glóssae* into *glossae collectae* and it is from these collections, the dictionary gradually developed, becoming increasingly systematized and alphabetized.⁶ This practice organises language and mutability, between: greek, latin and vulgar, between ages: classical and medieval, but also between disciplines: wether monastic or philosophical.

In the renaissance, a new, yet similar historical dialogue can be witnessed, which accompanied the accumulation of architectural knowledge. After the invention of the printing press and the redesccovery of classical texts, a transitional practice emerged, where historical knowledge was engaged with a practice of observation and documentation. Members of the *Accademia della Virtu*, an informal reading club, organised around Claudio Tolomei and concerned with questions about language and Poetry, tried to restore Vitruvius *De Archtiectura* by producing an annotated version and a translation in *volgara* – or common - language.⁷

It is in this time that the practice of Glossing seems to have been transposed from language to architecture, as early prints of Vitruvius’s text reveal margins intentionally left blank for readers to respond and contribute knowledge in the form of glosses: texts, drawings, and measurements. The *Corsini Incunabulum*, annotated by Giovanni Battista da Sangallo (1496–1548), exemplifies this practice: its margins left room to be enriched with writing, sketches, perspectives, plans, and sections that correspond to objects and locations mentioned in the classical text.⁸

In the process the *Accademia della Virtu* also gave Pliny some authority as a source for architectural knowledge, notably through editions of Vitruvius that aligned antiquarian scholarship with the humanist project of restoring classical design principles.⁹ Pliny was utilized, by the Sangallo Brothers for his descriptions of Rome, including dimensions, details and expositions about construction techniques which were dispersed throughout the book.¹⁰ Plinys descriptions of the wonders of the world became a locus of the imagination.

Another example, the annotated print of Palladio’s *I Quattro Libri dell’Architettura* by Inigo Jones

4 Camille, *Image on the Edge. The Margins of Medieval Art*, 11

5 Burnett, *Glosses and Commentaries on Arestotelian Logical Texts*, 77

6 McArthur, Tom. *Worlds of Reference: Lexicography, Learning and Language from the Clay Tablet to the Computer*, p. 76. Whereas the practice of collecting and defining finally culminated into a field of research and a profession of its own: Lexicography

7 Vanhaelen, ‘Cose di Platone fatte Toscane’: Language and Ideology in Two Vernacular Translations of Plato Printed by Francesco Priscianese, 1088

8 Tavares, *Anatomy of the Architectural Book*, 113

9 Fane-Saunders, *Pliny the Elder and the emergence of Renaissance architecture*, 187.

10 Fane-Saunders, *Pliny the Elder and the emergence of Renaissance architecture*, 6.

(1573–1652) demonstrates extensive use of the margins, which he employed for summaries, as well as comparisons and transcriptions of on-site dialogues with architects and craftsmen. Similarly to the medieval scribbles, the margins provided a space for a continuous commentary running throughout the work.¹¹

Historically, the use of glosses and marginalia created a dialogue between different forms of knowledge. Works such as Da Sangallo's *Incunabulum* and Inigo Jones's *Quattro Libri dell'Architettura* exemplify this interplay between empirical observation and theoretical ideals. Collected glosses and architectural publications show that annotation and commentary are not "marginal" practices but central mechanisms in the formation of knowledge. By recording, comparing, and expanding upon texts, scholars and architects created spaces in which disciplines could emerge and define their authority. Over time, the gloss - and, in the case of architecture, the sketch - developed into its own discursive practice, contributing to the creation of dictionaries, encyclopedias, and architectural canons. In this ongoing process, texts are repeatedly reinscribed and expanded, and the distinction between center and margin becomes increasingly unstable.

This also poses a question: where are the margins today? The bookmarkers, or the User Interface? The writing pad, with which the AI swallows your words? Who comments on who? Can we trace the dialogic process, now that nearly all text have been absorbed by the data vortex of ai?

11 Tavares, *Anatomy of the Architectural Book*, 113

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